

Simulators Comparison

Simulation Platform	Target Scale	Physics - Rendering Engine	Computational Overhead	ROS2 Integration	Primary Advantage & Use Case
Proposed Simulator	1/10 scale	Gazebo	Medium	Native ROS2	Best balance of physics, high-fidelity 3D rendering and bridge-free ROS2 networking; Future-proof
Legacy F1Tenth	1/10 scale	Gazebo Classic	Medium	ROS	Established legacy code, but built on end-of-life architecture (Gazebo Classic)
F1Tenth Gym	1/10 scale	2D PyBullet	Very Low	ROS/ROS2	Extremely fast 2D simulation, highly optimized for Reinforcement Learning training
CARLA/AutoDrive	Full-Scale Vehicles	Unreal Engine	Very High	Via Middleware (Bridge)	Unmatched photorealism, full-scale traffic AI, and city-scale environments